

THE ISSUE OF BORROWINGS IN SYNTACTIC PARADIGMATICS

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Abstract

This article discusses the historical development of syntactic theory and major approaches to syntax in linguistics. The study highlights the contributions of important scholars such as Ferdinand de Saussure, Lucien Tesnière, and Noam Chomsky. Special attention is paid to structural syntax, transformational grammar, and the distinction between language and speech. The article also examines modern issues related to media language and foreign linguistic influence.

Keywords: syntax, syntactic theory, transformational grammar, sentence structure, linguistic competence, media language.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada sintaktik nazariyaning tarixiy rivojlanishi va tilshunoslikdagi asosiy sintaktik yondashuvlar tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda Ferdinand de Sossyur, Lyusen Tesnyer va Noam Xomskiy kabi olimlarning sintaksis rivojiga qo'shgan hissasi yoritiladi. Struktur sintaksis, transformatsion grammatika hamda til va nutq o'rtasidagi farqlar alohida ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, media tili va xorijiy til elementlarining ta'siri bilan bog'liq zamonaviy masalalar ham tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sintaksis, sintaktik nazariya, transformatsion grammatika, gap tuzilishi, lingvistik kompetensiya, media tili.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются историческое развитие синтаксической теории и основные подходы к изучению синтаксиса в языкознании. Особое внимание уделяется вкладу таких ученых, как Фердинанд де Соссюр, Люсьен Теньер и Ноам Хомский. Анализируются структурный синтаксис, трансформационная грамматика, а также различие между языком и речью. Кроме того, затрагиваются современные проблемы языка СМИ и влияния иностранных языковых элементов.

Ключевые слова: синтаксис, синтаксическая теория, трансформационная грамматика, структура предложения, языковая компетенция, язык СМИ.

The scientific study of syntax originated with the ancient Greek philosophers' first attempts to classify and analyze judgements. The Stoics first used the word syntax, which comes from the ancient Greek word *sintaxis*, which means "military order" or "construction together," to describe the logical arrangement of words in the third century BC. The topic of syntax in the writings of Apollonius Dyscolus from the second century AD already covered linguistic events themselves, specifically the links between words and their forms in a sentence.

The distinction between psychological, logical, and grammatical concepts was unclear in linguistics until the late nineteenth century. The sentence was grammatically analyzed using predetermined logical categories, such as logical subject and grammatical subject, which were not distinguished. Syntax was seen as the study of how logical units and relationships are expressed in language, while phonetics and morphology were seen as the study of linguistic forms. This problem is mostly related to semantics in contemporary linguistics.

The French academics Antoine Arnauld and Claude Lancelot, who wrote the Port-Royal Grammar, were among the first to try to develop an explanatory syntactic theory in the seventeenth century, during the logical approach to language. In their perspective, linguistic events take on a particular shape because they mirror certain tenets of human reasoning. Under the influence of Wilhelm von Humboldt's philosophical approach to language, a psychological approach to grammar gained popularity in the

second half of the nineteenth century. H. Steinthal, H. Paul, and A.A. Potebnya, among others, represent this viewpoint and substituted psychological categories like "representation" for logical ones.

Ferdinand de Saussure made the distinction between language as an abstract system that underlies speech behavior and speech as the real manifestation of this system in human communication. Charles Bally differentiated language manifestations from speech manifestations within syntax, whereas V.V. Vinogradov contrasted the sentence's "building material," which consists of words and word combinations, with the sentence itself, which is a communicative unit with predicativity and modality. This issue continues to be relevant today. A. Gardiner, N.D. Arutyunova, V.A. Zvegintsev, and others further developed the distinction between the nominative ("language") and communicative ("speech") aspects of the sentence in their writings.

In the syntactic understanding of N.Yu. Shvedova, the opposition between sentence and phrase was conveyed by the contrast between abstract structural schemes that define sentences and subordinate relationships that define the structure of phrases.

Mathesius, building upon the concepts of Weil, Paul, and other nineteenth-century linguists, showed that syntax reflects two distinct kinds of speaker behavior that correspond to two different forms of sentence division: grammatical division, such the division into subject and predicate, and real division into theme and rheme. The rheme includes the novel information being conveyed, and the theme serves as the message's beginning point.

Lucien Tesnière, the inventor of the concept of "structural syntax," created a universal sentence model based on a number of core ideas, including the universality and unidirectionality of syntactic relationships, the existence of a single grammatical center in the sentence represented by the verb, the dependence of sentence structure on the combinability of the verb, the non-uniqueness of representing structural hierarchy through linear syntactic sequences, and the distinction between participants of the situation (actants) and circumstances (circonstants).

The publication of Noam Chomsky's book *Syntactic Structures* in 1957 marked a significant turning point in the field of syntax. Chomsky's name is linked not only with generative grammar as a linguistic theory but also with a radical change in how language is studied, specifically the move away from primarily descriptive methods and toward explanatory methods that emphasize theoretical interpretation.

In his first book, Chomsky described language as a system that can produce an infinite number of sentences using a finite set of grammatical resources. To this end, he created the ideas of deep structure and surface structure, as well as transformations that explain the movement from deep structures to surface structures.

In his book *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax* (1965), Chomsky outlined the "Aspects Model," or conventional theory, which attempted to include a semantic element into the formal model by adding semantic interpretation rules that give meaning to deep structures.

Additionally, Chomsky made a crucial distinction between performance and competence. A speaker's potential knowledge of language is represented by linguistic competence, while the actual processes involved in using this competence in speech behavior are represented by linguistic performance. Chomsky asserts that competence is the most important factor because it influences performance.

According to transformational grammar's core argument, an adequate grammatical theory must differentiate between fundamental structure and surface syntactic structure, as well as between deep grammar and surface grammar.

The syntactic aspect of grammar, or language theory, is viewed as a set of guidelines that either allow or mandate specific actions with elements of a given kind. These terminal components are seen as the smallest units of meaning organized by syntax. These basic units are referred to as formatives by Chomsky.

Despite the fact that Chomsky's perspective gained widespread popularity, it has not been universally embraced. Other significant syntactic theories include categorial grammar, the theory of

principles and parameters, functional syntactic typology, and syntax within the "Meaning ↔ Text" model, in addition to generative grammar. However, a thorough examination of these ideas is outside the purview of this paper.

The notion that every statement can be seen as a unit that belongs to many interacting paradigms simultaneously is becoming more prevalent: syntactic, actualizational, and transformational (interpretative). Differences in the way categories are expressed, such as:

- tense;
- mode;
- affirmation and rejection;
- both interrogative and non-interrogative forms;
- grammatical viewpoint of the sentence, taking into account activity, semi-activity, passivity, and semi-passivity.

The components that make up a sentence paradigm may also vary in how the semantic topic, actual division, and other features are represented, as long as the semantic invariant's identity is maintained.

The idea of the syntactic field of a sentence was first proposed by G.A. Zolotova, who also created the accompanying theory. Her approach posits that the field's nuclear statement presents the scenario in an unbiased and efficient way. According to Zolotova, nuclear sentences should reflect "the unity of syntactic, morphological, and semantic characteristics within their structure." Words belonging to isosemic subclasses are the only ones used in such statements.

By introducing the notion of isosemy into syntactic theory, G.A. Zolotova demonstrates that subclasses of words can be divided into isosemic and non-isosemic depending on whether the semantics of the subclass corresponds to the main semantics of a particular component of speech. Words of isosemic and non-isosemic subclasses are used to name referents directly and indirectly, respectively. In syntax, isosemy refers to the relationship between the categorical meanings of structural sentence components and the categorical meanings of their denotations in objective reality.

It is necessary to highlight the significance of more multidimensional analysis and description of media language, as well as clarification of its impact on linguistic competency, notably on the development of linguistic competence among younger generations, in the face of the decline in general cultural and linguistic culture.

As a result, there are still many unanswered and relevant questions concerning the operation of the Russian language, particularly those pertaining to the intrusion of foreign linguistic components brought about by a complicated interplay of linguistic, psychological, social, national, and other factors.

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